

USE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROVISION OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6462990>

Tokhirov Javlon Rakhimovich

Bukhara State University

lecturer of the department “Economics of the service sector”.

Bukhara State University, 3-2-economics-20

group student, Gafurov Ruzijon

Abstract: *This article focuses on the use of information and communication technologies in the provision of educational services, and analyzes the possibilities of using 7 platforms in the provision of online educational services. Summarizing the results of the analysis, general conclusions were reached on the use of platforms.*

Keywords: *Education, educational services, online education, Moodle, iSpring Learn, WebTutor, Teachbase, GetCourse, iSpring Market, Memberlux.*

Improving the skills of staff in educational institutions based on the responsibilities of the position on the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) is a pressing issue today. In this regard, we consider it expedient to organize courses and work, taking into account the requirements of ICT literacy at 3 levels for competent employees in the workplace (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Requirements for ICT literacy of employees at different levels

As a result of our research, we would like to suggest the following formulas for determining the level of ICT provision of services and solving problems on the material and technical base:

$$ICTal = \frac{ICTt * 100}{Ne} \quad (1)$$

This: $ICTal$ – Average level of information and communication technology;
 $ICTt$ – Number of information and communication technology tools;
 Ne – Number of employees.

$$ICTe = \frac{Q * 100}{ICTac} \quad (2)$$

This: $ICTe$ – Effectiveness of information and communication technologies;
 Q – Volume of services provided (gross revenue);
 $ICTac$ – Average cost of information and communication technologies.

$$ICTp = \frac{SR * 100}{ICTac} \quad (3)$$

This: $ICTp$ – Profitability of information and communication technologies;
 SR – Net profit from services rendered;
 $ICTac$ – Average cost of information and communication technologies.

Studies by industry scholars predict that investment in online education should reach \$350 billion by 2025, but this figure is now expected to rise significantly to \$1 trillion. In preparation for this study, we examined common online education platforms and attempted to determine their potential to improve the quality of education.

First of all, we were interested in what online platforms students and university professors use. In our opinion, the problem begins here, when switching to online education, first of all, it becomes necessary to study the educational platforms of this form and the world experience in this area.

The online education market is very diverse. These include open online courses, including general education platforms, mobile applications and computer games for learning, video conferencing, virtual lessons with teachers, and more. It is more important to understand the capabilities of the platforms. To achieve the best results, it is necessary to have the skills to correctly combine formats and tools. To date, several platforms are used in the provision of online education services (Table 1).

Table 1.

General classification of 7 platforms used in online education

	Platform	Feature
.	Moodle	Free platform with extensive customization options. Installed only on your server. There are many plugins to extend functionality. Requires web development skills for administration.
.	iSpring Learn	A platform focused on the corporate sector. Ready to work immediately after registration. Support for all types of training materials, webinars, detailed statistics and a course editor that allows you to quickly create courses and simulators from office documents and videos.
.	WebTutor	A modular HRM platform that allows not only to build training, but also all HR processes: competency assessment, automate the selection and initial training of personnel. A complex system with a wide range of possibilities.

.	Teachbase	Cloud learning platform. There is a built-in course editor - the page with the course is assembled on Tilda, like a regular landing page. It is possible to sell courses.
.	GetCourse	The most popular platform among information businessmen. Webinars, integration with many payment systems, protection against theft of courses.
.	iSpring Market	A platform for creating your own online school. The service provides a constructor and marketplace for online courses and does not charge a commission on sales.
.	Memberluxe	A plugin for WordPress that allows you to create a learning portal based on a regular website. One-time payment, suitable for beginners infobusinessmen.

Moodle features

Platform customization via plugins. The functionality and design of Moodle is changed with the help of plugins that can be downloaded for free from the Internet or created by yourself.

Open source system. Anyone can develop. As a rule, plugins are developed by users themselves, and then posted on the Internet for general access.

Integration with other services. Moodle is easy to integrate with other platforms like WordPress or Zoom webinars.

iSpring Features

Course constructor. Using iSpring Suite, you can create educational content: courses, tests, interactive simulators and screencasts.

Unlimited storage. You can upload an unlimited number of files to iSpring Learn.

Integration with other services. iSpring Learn easily integrates with other customer systems through an open API. For example, it can be a personnel system or a corporate portal.

Fast platform launch. The platform does not need to be configured for a long time. It is enough to register, download courses and invite users.

WebTutor Features

Platform customization via modules. WebTutor offers modules - separate programs with functionality. For example, there are modules for distance learning, recruitment, webinar room, chat bots. There are 12 modules in total, each is paid separately.

Integration with other systems. WebTutor can be integrated with the client's IT infrastructure systems: 1C, Oracle EBS, SAP HR, etc.

Course constructor. WebSoft has a CourseLab course builder, which is purchased separately. It can be used to create educational content.

Teachbase Features

Integration with other systems. Teachbase can be integrated with third party CRM and payment systems.

Platform for webinars. Teachbase allows you to conduct webinars directly on the platform without third-party services.

GetCourse Features

Sale of courses. On GetCourse, you can sell trainings and webinars, create mailing lists, and track sales performance.

Automation of business processes. GetCourse does all the routine work for info businessmen: it reminds students about the upcoming webinar, checks tests, and issues certificates to users after successfully completing the course.

Features of iSpring Market

SEO-optimization of courses. In the course settings, you can add SEO titles and tags to make the page indexed and make it easier for customers to find it in Google and Yandex.

Ready showcase with courses. This is your school's main page, where you can see all online courses. You can arrange it according to your course, group the courses into categories and specify the price for each.

Gamification. You can further motivate your students with rankings, virtual and real rewards. For example, for academic success, the system will open free access to an additional lesson or master class.

Accepting payments without commission. In iSpring Market, customers pay in any convenient way: with a bank card or with an electronic wallet. For example, through Pay Pal, Stripe, Yukassa, Robokassa, PayAnyWay and Tinkoff. The system does not charge a commission for the transfer.

Detailed analytics. The system will generate reports on student engagement and show which materials are most in demand. And with the help of sales reports, you can see which total revenue, which courses are bought more and from which channels customers come more often.

Certificates. In iSpring Market, you can open a certification center: conduct exams and issue professional retraining diplomas. As soon as the client completes the course, the system will automatically send a personalized certificate. You don't have to spend time on this.

Memberlux Features

Plugin for WordPress. Memberlux is installed on a WordPress site, allowing you to sell courses on your site.

Integration with other services. Memberlux can be integrated with payment systems and mailing services.

Material protection. Video encryption works in Memberlux: you can't download it or view the code. Thus, your content is protected and no one will steal it.

Based on our research, we decided to examine the strengths of the 9-criteria indicators to evaluate the platforms used in online learning (Table 2).

Table 2.

Comparative characteristics of platforms used in online learning in terms of functionality

Criterion	Memberlux	iSpring	Teachbase	WebTutor	GetCourse	Memberlux
Content	+	+	+	+	+	-

Creation						
Sale of courses	+	-	+	-	+	+
Mobile learning	+	+	+	+	+	+
Webinars	+	+	+	+	+	-
SCORM support	+	+	+	+	-	-
Gamification	+	+	-	+	+	-
Branding	+	+	+	+	+	+
Cloud version	+	+	+	-	+	-
Boxed version	+	+	-	+	-	+

With the onset of the pandemic, the world's leading universities have developed and are implementing plans to introduce blended courses. Because classical lessons are complemented by work on the online platform. This decision is motivated not only by the need to prepare for the continuation of the pandemic, but also by objective reasons. In particular, according to a survey conducted in the United States, 81 percent of students believe that the use of assistive digital devices significantly improves the quality of education and academic performance.

In particular, the online form of education should never surpass the traditional form of education, which has a history of almost three thousand years, in the next hundred years. Online education will remain a tool that complements traditional education and increases its effectiveness. Throughout our lives, we need to constantly acquire new knowledge and skills, and in a specific period allotted for education, this, of course, cannot be achieved. That is why we will continue to learn during our other efforts to create a comfortable environment for work and life, in which case online learning becomes a very important tool. The remote format is a very convenient tool for developing unique narrow skills, getting to know new applications and digital tools. During the pandemic, there has been a rapid development of special skills, with all sections of society eager to learn some new skill.

REFERENCES:

1. Boettcher, J. V., & Conrad, R.-M. The online teaching survival guide: Simple and practical pedagogical tips. John Wiley & Sons. 2010.
2. Bowen, W. G., & Ithaka, S. Interactive learning online at public universities: Evidence from randomized trials. Ithaka S+R. Retrieved from <http://mitcet.mit.edu/wpcontent/uploads/2012/05/BowenReport-2012.pdf>. 2012.
3. Hamari, J., Koivisto, J., Sarsa, H., & Hamari, J. Does Gamification Work. In A Literature Review of Empirical Studies on gamification. In proceedings of the 47th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, Hawaii, USA. 2014.
4. Lack, K. A. Current status of research on online learning in postsecondary education. 2012.
5. Landers, R. N., & Callan, R. C. Casual social games as serious games: The psychology of gamification in undergraduate education and employee training. In Serious games and edutainment applications (pp. 399–423). Springer. 2011.
6. Xu, D., Huang, W. W., Wang, H., & Heales, J. Enhancing e-learning effectiveness using an intelligent agent-supported personalized virtual learning environment: An empirical investigation. *Information & Management*, 51(4), 430–440. 2014.
7. Student, T. J. R. P. THE EFFECTIVE USE OF STATE-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES Tokhirov JR Email: Tokhirov684@scientifictext.ru.
8. Rakhimovich, T. J. DEVELOPMENT AND SUPPORTING OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES. GWALIOR MANAGEMENT ACADEMY, 69.
9. Тохиров, Ж. Р. (2016). ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ СИСТЕМ И ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В СЕЛЬСКОМ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕ. In Аграрная наука-сельскому хозяйству (pp. 297-298).